

Documentation of actinopterygii (ray-finned fish), and decapods (crabs and shrimps) found in Dapeng, Shenzhen

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Abstract

Dapeng is a district located in the easternmost extremity of Shenzhen and to the northeast of Hong Kong. We went to a fish farm raft located in Dapeng to collect specimens and observe the district's biodiversity. In order to assess the impact of human activity on the local environment, I decided to launch a complete investigation and guide to the marine organisms inhabiting the area, observing what species have adapted to this polluted environment.

Additional keywords: Shenzhen, Dapeng, Biofouling, Pollution, Biodiversity, Geography

1. Introduction

Dapeng, also known as "Dapeng Peninsula", is a district located in the southeast of Shenzhen City, surrounded by sea, facing Daya Bay in the east, bordering Huizhou, connecting Dapeng Bay in the west, and just across the New Territories of Hong Kong. It is an important part of the Guangdong-Hong Kong-Macao Greater Bay Area. The area is 600 square kilometers, of which the land area is 295 square kilometers, accounting for about one-sixth of Shenzhen. The sea area is 305 square kilometers, accounting for about one-fourth of Shenzhen, and the coastline is 128 kilometers long, accounting for about half of the city [1].

1.1. Geography and topography

Dapeng consists mostly of coastal mountain ranges, siltstone, and shale. Beaches, islands, reefs, sea cliffs, caves, bridges, pillars, and other marine erosion landforms are well-developed. The east and west sides of Dapeng are bordered by the sea, and the north and south areas are surrounded by mountains. The area has a higher altitude than the lowlands, and the terrain is rather complex. The natural landforms of Dapeng are mainly coastal low mountains and hills, mostly covered by residual sloping breccias and thin, red soil-type weathering crusts. Wide valleys and small plains are scattered between the mountains and the seashore [2].

1.2. Hydrology

The rivers in Dapeng New District have short steep slopes, and their runoff, flow, flood peaks, and precipitation are closely related, they are all rain-sourced rivers; the water system is divided into the bay water system. Many of these rivers are under the jurisdiction of the Nanao Sub-district, and all of them flow into the sea from the mountainous area. The larger rivers include the Nan'ao River, Xinda River, and Wangmu River [2].

1.3. Climate

Affected by the ocean, Dapeng is often rainy, and foggy and is sometimes hit by typhoons. The northern and southern parts are prone to sudden and heavy precipitation, and the risk of geological disasters is relatively high. Due to the high vegetation coverage and the regulating effect of the ocean, the average temperature is mild at 22.5°C, and the urban heat intensity is relatively small. The wind speed is relatively large, with an average wind speed of 2.5 meters per second.

1.4. Fauna and flora

According to a survey in 2018, there are 218 species of terrestrial vertebrates in Dapeng. There are 40 species protected at the provincial level or above. In marine biomes, the coverage rate of coral reefs in Dapeng Bay and Daya Bay has reached 50%, of which all stony corals belong to the second-level national protected animals category and are included in the world's "Convention on International Trade in Endangered Species of Wild Fauna and Flora" (CITES Convention). The four coral groups identified so far are the Tai O Bay Hard Coral Area, the Dalugang Reef Area in Nanao, the Dongxiyong Reef Area, and the Yangmeikeng Reef Area (information from NMMBA and Baidu). Dapeng has 1105 species of plants including 153 species of rare and endangered plants, including 16 species that are nationally protected [2].

1.5. Pollution

According to a maritime study, nearly half of Shenzhen's coastal waters were seriously contaminated last year, and multiple sewage drainage lines were found to be discharging excessive pollutants into Dapeng.

2. Sampling methods

The sampling location is a floating fish raft belonging to the China Academy of Fishery Sciences South China Sea Fisheries Research Institute Shenzhen Test Base, Dapeng (Figure 1). Data were collected during the autumn and winter of 2022, under sunny weather conditions, and with average temperatures 30 °C. Salinity stood at 1.015-1.020, and the water temperature at 26 °C. The fish raft was located in a recessed estuary bank. There were multiple rocky shores and fish rafts (for marine organism farming) scattered throughout this geographical range. The predicted underwater environment was muddy

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bottoms with rocks, typically referring to a brackish environment. The ropes and objects connected to the fish raft had wide biodiversity of sea squirts (Ascidians), sponges (Porifera), and bryozoan attached to them, providing a habitat for an abundance of additional organisms such as crabs, shrimps, which isopods (Isopoda), amphipods (Amphipoda), barnacles (Balanomorpha), nudibranch (Nudibranchia), and many other species (Figure 2). The organisms collected in this research were either caught from crab traps hanging off the fish raft, hand-caught from biofouling matter or fished with *Nereis* as bait. Specimens were brought back to the laboratory by keeping the water oxygen-rich with an air pump, and the temperature at a suitable temperature for organism survival by putting ice packs in the box. The specimens were kept alive and stored in a fish pool at the lab (Figure 3) for further examination, identification, and photography. The fish species identification was based on the information provided by HK Fish Net [3], a website that documents fish species found in Hong Kong. Since the biodiversity of fish in the sampling location is similar to that of Hong Kong, the website was utilized to validate the species names and assist in identifying the species accurately. By cross-referencing the observed fish species with the information on HK Fish Net, a reliable identification process was ensured.

3. Results

In this paper, we have decided to cover the class Actinopterygii (ray-finned fishes) because of a lack of data on Chondrichthyes (cartilaginous fishes). For decapods, I have covered Brachyura (crabs) and Caridea (shrimps), also because of missing data on Paguroidea (Hermit Crabs) (A Porcellanidae was recorded: *Pachycheles*). The fish raft had a well-developed biodiversity, home to many ascidians, bryozoa, and Porifera. However, because of a lack of specimens and a high risk of misidentification, we decided to exclude other organisms in this document.

3.1. Actinopterygii (ray-finned fishes)

3.1.1 Species name: Mangrove red snapper - *Lutjanus argentimaculatus* (Forsskål, 1775)

Classification: *Lutjanidae*; *Lutjaninae*; *Lutjanus* (Figure 4)

3.1.2 Species name: Emperor red snapper - *Lutjanus sebae* (Cuvier, 1816)

Classification: *Lutjanidae*; *Lutjaninae*; *Lutjanus* (Figure 5)

3.1.3 Species name: Star snapper - *Lutjanus stellatus* Akazaki, 1983

Classification: *Lutjanidae*; *Lutjaninae*; *Lutjanus* (Figure 6)

3.1.4 Species name: Goldlined seabream - *Rhabdosargus sarba* (Forsskål, 1775)

Classification: *Sparidae*; *Rhabdosargus* (Figure 7)

3.1.5 Species name: Regal demoiselle - *Neopomacentrus cyanomos* (Bleeker, 1856)

Classification: *Pomacentridae*; *Neopomacentrus* (Figure 8)

3.1.6 Species name: Chinese demoiselle - *Neopomacentrus bankieri* (Richardson, 1846)

Classification: *Pomacentridae*; *Neopomacentrus* (Figure 9)

3.1.7 Species name: Indo-Pacific sergeant - *Abudefduf vaigiensis* (Quoy & Gaimard, 1825)

Classification: *Pomacentridae*; *Abudefduf* (Figure 10)

3.1.8 Species name: Blenny species - cf. *Entomacrodus* sp.

Classification: *Blenniidae*; *Salariinae*; *Entomacrodus* (Figure 11)

3.1.9 Species name: White-spotted spinefoot - *Siganus cf. canaliculatus* (Park, 1797)

Classification: *Siganidae*; *Siganus*; (Figure 12)

3.1.10 Species name: Fan-bellied leatherjacket - *Monacanthus chinensis* (Osbeck, 1765)

Classification: *Monacanthidae*; *Monacanthus*; (Figure 13)

3.1.11 Species name: White-spotted pufferfish - *Arothron hispidus* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Classification: *Tetraodontidae*; *Arothron*; (Figure 14)

3.2. Decapoda (Crabs and Shrimps)

3.2.1 Species name: Peppermint shrimp - *Lysmata cf. vittata* (Stimpson, 1860)

Classification: *Hippolytidae*; *Lysmata*; (Figure 15)

3.2.2 Species name: Pistol shrimp species - cf. *Alpheus* sp.

Classification: *Alpheidae*; *Alpheus*; (Figure 16)

Figure 1. The fish farm sampling site. **a.** The geographical location of the sampling site. It is in the Estuary region of a lagoon surrounded by Dapeng. **b.** The geographical coverage of the investigation. The floating object in the range is the fish raft.

Figure 2. Images are taken when collecting in the field. **(a) & (b):** The geographical formations next to the sampling site. **(c) (d) (e) (f) (g)** biofouling matter on ropes and hanging objects in the water. **(h)** a fresh *Liomera rugata* specimen. **(i)** Dr. Tim Wong holding two bricks full of biofouling organisms. **(j) (k)** The transportation of specimens.

Figure 3. Specimen storing method: **a.** The complete set-up fish pond. The different boxes contain different species that need to be separated for special care. **b.** the assembled body of the fish pond. **c.** Different species are separated in small containers. **d.** the freshly collected fish are stored in a basket with holes enabling water flow.

3.2.3 Species name: Porcelain crab species - cf. *Pachycheles* sp.

Classification: Porcellanidae; *Pachycheles*; (Figure 17)

3.2.4 Species name: Dark-fingered crab - *Chlorodiella nigra* (Forskål, 1775)

Classification: Xanthidae; *Chlorodiella*; (Figure 18)

Figure 4. Several juvenile specimens were spotted roaming in shallow waters around the biofouling matter. Adults were observed in captivity in nearby open-water fish pens. The juveniles presumably escaped from the nets. Pictured is a juvenile specimen collected elsewhere.

Figure 5. Large adult specimens have been caught by casting rods. Presumably escaped from the fish pens.

Figure 6. Large adult specimens have been caught by casting rods. Presumably escaped from the fish pens. Pictured is a juvenile specimen collected elsewhere.

3.2.5 Species name: Decorator crab species - *Majidae* sp.

Classification: Majidae; (Figure 19)

Figure 7. Juvenile specimens have been caught by casting rods. Presumably escaped from the fish pens. Pictured is a juvenile specimen collected elsewhere.

Figure 8. A school of specimens was spotted roaming in shallow waters around the biofouling matter. Several specimens were collected by fishing. Pictured is an adult specimen collected elsewhere.

Figure 9. A school of specimens was spotted roaming in shallow waters around the biofouling matter. Several specimens were collected by fishing. Pictured is an adult specimen collected elsewhere.

3.2.6 Species name: Swimming crab species - *Thalamita* sp.

Classification: Portunidae; Thalamitinae; *Thalamita* (Figure 20)

Figure 10. A juvenile specimen was observed roaming under a tire covered in biofouling. Pictured is an adult specimen collected elsewhere.

Figure 11. This specimen was collected when lifting biofouling matter.

Figure 12. A school of specimens was spotted roaming in shallow waters around the biofouling matter. An adult specimen was collected by fishing. There were specimens kept in captivity in the fish farm and there was also a wild population of this species in the area. Pictured is an adult specimen collected elsewhere.

3.2.7 Species name: Asian paddle crab - *Charybdis cf. japonica* (A. Milne-Edwards, 1861)

Classification: Portunidae; Thalamitinae; *Charybdis* (Figure 21)

Figure 13. A juvenile specimen was obtained when lifting biofouling matter. Pictured is a juvenile specimen collected elsewhere.

Figure 14. Several juvenile specimens were obtained using a crab trap hanging midwater using breadcrumbs as bait. Left pictured are two juvenile specimens collected in Dapeng. The right shows a juvenile specimen collected elsewhere.

Figure 15. Several specimens were obtained when lifting biofouling matter. There is a stable community of this species associated with biofouling. Currently identified as *L. vittata* Stimpson.

3.2.8 Species name: Corrugated liomera - *Liomera cf. rugata* (H. Milne Edwards, 1834)

Classification: Xanthidae; *Liomera* (Figure 22)

4. Discussion

The three *Lutjanus* species collected in our documentation had most probably escaped from the fish farm, as other than the specimens collected by fishing outside the farm,

Figure 16. Several specimens were obtained when lifting biofouling matter. There is a stable community of this species associated with biofouling. The pictured specimen is a specimen of the same species collected later in the year.

Figure 17. A specimen was obtained when lifting biofouling matter.

Figure 18. A specimen was obtained when lifting biofouling matter.

there were specimens in the breeding cages too. *Lutjanus* are tough fishes that adapt to brackish environments. The *Neopomacentrus*, *Abudefduf*, *Entomacrodus*, *Arothron*, and *Monacanthus* are also well-expected species as we have also collected them in similar environments on other occasions. They are all *Euryhaline* species (some juveniles) that adapt well to brackish environments and pollutant waters. Much like crustaceans, *Alpheus*, *Thalamita*, Charyb-

Figure 19. A specimen with a barnacle attached was obtained when lifting biofouling matter.

Figure 20. A specimen was obtained when scooping using a net near a cement wall covered in barnacles.

Figure 21. Several specimens were obtained when scooping using a net near a cement wall covered in barnacles. Currently identified as *C. japonica* A. Milne-Edwards.

dis, *Grapsus*, *Chlorodiella*, *Majidae*, and *Pachycheles* are not rare finds. These crustaceans inhabit almost all marine

Figure 22. two specimens were obtained when lifting biofouling matter. Currently identified as *L. rugata* H. Milne Edwards.

environments and are quite resistant to polluted waters. The unexpected species collected on this trip were *Lysmata* and *Liomera* species. I assumed these species do not inhabit brackish areas and polluted water at relatively high temperatures. However there was an incredibly diverse population of the aforementioned species, so I assumed they are also well-adapted to the environment. The fouling community system provides a habitat for a great diversity of marine organisms including echinoderms, *amphipods*, *isopods*, and many others. In this paper, we only documented the fish, crabs, and shrimps observed at the sampling site. We found that there is a high diversity and population of crustaceans, much higher than on rocky shores and beaches. We argue that the diverse fouling system has provided food and shelter for these smaller creatures and that they attract larger predators such as the fish documented in the paper. In conclusion, the fouling system has a diverse food web and provides shelter for many organisms, playing an important role in the marine ecosystem.

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